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Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance and intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy (IPTp) for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance and intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy (IPTp) for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy: A systematic review and meta-analysis

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2 Executive summary

2.1 Background

The World Health Organization recommends that women living in malaria-endemic areas receive intermittent preventive treatment during the second and third trimesters of pregnancy (IPTp) with an effective antimalarial. Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) is currently the only antimalarial recommended by WHO for IPTp. A meta-analysis of four trials conducted before the widespread introduction of IPTp-SP as policy showed that IPTp-SP was associated with a 62% reduction in placental malaria, 36% reduction in maternal anaemia, a 19% reduction in low birthweight among paucigravidae, and a 105g increase in mean birth weight. A subsequent meta-analysis of 7 trials comparing monthly vs 2-dose IPTp-SP showed that three or more doses of IPTp-SP were associated with a 49% greater reduction in placental malaria, a 20% greater reduction in LBW, and a 56g greater increase in mean birthweight than 2-dose IPTp-SP. However, resistance of *Plasmodium falciparum* to sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine threatens the antimalarial effectiveness of IPTp in sub-Saharan Africa. We aimed to provide an update of a previous review of the associations between markers of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance in *P. falciparum* and the effectiveness of IPTp-SP for malaria-associated outcomes.

2.2 Methods

We searched databases (from January 1, 1990, to September 9, 2021) for observational studies or trials that reported data on low birth weight, anaemia and malaria by IPTp-SP dose. Studies or study arms that involved only HIV-infected women or combined interventions were excluded. We then searched for studies, matched by study period (\pm 3 years) and location, that reported on molecular markers of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance, as indicated by Ala437Gly, Lys540Glu, and Ala581Gly substitutions in the *dhps* gene. Two-stage random-effects meta-analyses were performed using weighted mixed-effects models for nonlinear trend estimation of summarised dose-response data, and results were expressed as mean difference (inverse variance) or relative risk reduction [RRR] (Mantel-Haenszel) per dose-step increase. Multivariate meta-regression was used to explore the modifying effects of SP resistance on IPTp-SP effectiveness. Resistance was defined as low (Ala437Gly <75% in Central/West Africa or Lys540Glu <40% in East/southern Africa), medium (Ala437Gly \geq 75% in Central/West Africa or Lys540Glu 40-60% and Ala581Gly <5% in East/southern Africa), high (Lys540Glu \geq 60 & Ala581Gly <5% in East/Southern Africa) and very-high (Lys540Glu \geq 60% and *dhps* Ala581Gly \geq 5% in East/Southern Africa). Malaria transmission intensity was expressed as *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ based on the malaria atlas project data matched by study period and location. This study is registered with PROSPERO, number CRD42021250359. Adverse events were evaluated from trials only.

2.3 Findings

Overall, 102 studies and 105,276 participants contributed to this study.

2.3.1 Maternal and placental malaria infection at delivery

Overall, IPTp-SP was associated with a 20% reduction in placental or maternal malaria at delivery detected by any diagnostic test (all gravidae) per dose (95% CI 16–24%, $I^2=73%$, 94 studies). This was 24% (19–29%, $I^2=59%$, 53 studies) in paucigravidae and 17% (13–20%, $I^2=1%$, 41 studies) in multigravidae. There was a clear trend toward reduced efficacy with increased resistance. The relative risk reduction reduced from 28% (95% CI 20–36) in the lowest resistance strata to 22% (14–29), 8% (0–7) and -5% (-16, 5) in the moderate, high and very high resistance strata, respectively. Malaria transmission intensity (*PfPR*₂₋₁₀) was not a significant effect modifier of the effectiveness of SP.

2.3.2 Maternal anaemia and haemoglobin

IPTp-SP was associated with a 10% reduction in anaemia (95% CI 8-13%, I^2 70%, 53 studies) and a 0.19 g/dl increase in mean haemoglobin per dose of SP (95% CI 0.15-0.22, I^2 1%, 46 studies). The effect decreased within increasing SP resistance but remained associated with significant protective efficacy (RRR=8.2%, 95% CI 3-13%, I^2 0%, 5 studies) in the highest SP resistance areas.

2.3.3 Birthweight

IPTp-SP was associated with a 25% reduction in low birth weight overall (all gravidae) (95% CI 22–29%, I^2 =71%, p <0.0001, 98 studies) and 26% in paucigravidae (95% CI 21–31%, I^2 =62%, 59 studies) and 21% in multigravidae (95% CI 16–26%, I^2 =45%, 49 studies). IPTp-SP was also associated with a mean increase in birth weight of 57 grams per dose among all gravidae (95% CI 44-69 grams, I^2 56%, 82 studies), 67g among paucigravidae (95% CI 50-85 grams, I^2 44%, 62 studies) and 43g among multigravidae (43 grams, 95% CI 26-60 grams, I^2 47%, 45 studies). The RRR decreased within increasing SP resistance but remained associated with reductions in LBW in high resistance areas (RRR=23%, 95% CI 16-29, I^2 =59%, 15 studies), but not in the highest resistance areas (RRR=16%, 95% CI -4, 32, I^2 =69%, 6 studies). Mean difference in birthweight was 65 grams (95% CI 44- 87), 66 grams (95% CI 45-88), 46 grams (95% CI 27-66) in the lowest, middle, and high SP resistance areas, with a non-significant mean difference of 11 gm (95% CI -9-32 gm) in the highest resistance areas. However, the number of studies in the highest resistance areas with information on birthweight was small (N=6 for LBW and N=7 for mean birthweight).

2.3.4 Adverse events

The pooled prevalence of serious adverse events among IPTp-SP recipients was 3.84% (95% CI 2.20-5.88, 8 trials). The pooled prevalence of adverse events was 14.3% (95% CI 4.9-27.5%) (16 trials, 8122 participants). In two trials comparing IPTp-SP vs placebo or case-management, the pooled risk ratio of an adverse event was 0.56 (95% CI 0.30-1.01) in favour of IPTp-SP. Skin reactions were rare, with a pooled prevalence of 0.4% (95% CI 0.2-0.7) among all women who took IPTp-SP (11 trials, 4186 participants), with no significant increase seen in the two trials comparing IPTp-SP with placebo/ case management (pooled RR 1.24, 95% CI 0.34-4.58).

2.3.5 Clinical trials comparing IPTp with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) vs SP.

A recent IPD meta-analysis of six trials comparing IPTp with DP vs SP showed that IPTp with DP is superior to SP in reducing malaria, preventing about two out of every three infections relative to SP. However, this did not translate into better pregnancy outcomes, primarily because SP was associated with better fetal growth, resulting in higher mean birthweights in all gravidae groups. Although the mechanism of how SP may promote fetal growth requires further research, there was some indication that this is mediated, at least in part, by improved gestational weight gain in the mother. (Results presented separately.)

2.4 Interpretation

The effectiveness of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp to clear existing infections and prevent new ones is severely compromised in areas with high and very high resistance to SP. However, IPTp-SP remains associated with reductions in low birth weight and maternal anaemia in these areas. This, combined with evidence from recently completed trials comparing IPTp with DP suggests that SP may have potent non-malarial effects. IPTp-SP should continue to be used in high SP resistant areas until more effective alternatives for malaria chemoprevention are found. Further studies are needed to elucidate the non-malarial effects of SP. In addition, further trials are required to explore the combination of SP + DP for IPTp to benefit from the superior antimalarial efficacy of DP and the potent non-malarial effects of SP on fetal growth.

3 GRADE assessment of key outcomes

Certainty assessment							No of patients		Effect		Certainty	Importance
No of studies	Study design	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations	therapeutic courses of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine	no medicine	Relative (95% CI)	Absolute (95% CI)		
Low birth weight, per dose of SP												
98	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	strong association dose response gradient	0/0	2.5%	RR 0.75 (0.71 to 0.78)	6 fewer per 1,000 (from 7 fewer to 6 fewer)	⊕⊕○○ Moderate	CRITICAL
								56.7%		142 fewer per 1,000 (from 164 fewer to 125 fewer)		
Maternal anaemia, per dose of SP												
53	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	dose response gradient	0/0	10.8%	RR 0.90 (0.87 to 0.93)	11 fewer per 1,000 (from 14 fewer to 8 fewer)	⊕⊕○○ Low	CRITICAL
								66.0%		66 fewer per 1,000 (from 86 fewer to 46 fewer)		
Maternal malaria infection at delivery, per dose of SP (assessed with: Microscopy, RDT, or PCR)												
72	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	strong association dose response gradient	0/0	2.0%	RR 0.80 (0.75 to 0.85)	4 fewer per 1,000 (from 5 fewer to 3 fewer)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	CRITICAL
								70.3%		141 fewer per 1,000 (from 176 fewer to 105 fewer)		
Placental malaria infection												
76	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	strong association dose response gradient	0/0	0.9%	RR 0.78 (0.74 to 0.84)	2 fewer per 1,000 (from 2 fewer to 1 fewer)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	CRITICAL
								86.9%		191 fewer per 1,000 (from 226 fewer to 139 fewer)		
Mean birthweight, per dose of SP												
82	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	strong association dose response gradient	0	0	-	MD 57 grams higher (44 higher to 69 higher)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	NOT IMPORTANT
Preterm delivery, per dose of SP												
59	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	dose response gradient	0/0	1.6%	RR 0.76 (0.71 to 0.81)	4 fewer per 1,000 (from 5 fewer to 3 fewer)	⊕⊕○○ Low	NOT IMPORTANT
								75.7%		182 fewer per 1,000 (from 220 fewer to 144 fewer)		
Maternal haemoglobin, per dose of SP												
46	observational studies	serious ^a	not serious	not serious	not serious	dose response gradient	0	0	-	MD 0.19 g/dl higher (0.15 higher to 0.22 higher)	⊕⊕○○ Low	NOT IMPORTANT
Stillbirths and/or abortions												
46	observational studies	serious ^a	serious ^b	serious ^c	not serious	none	0/0	1.0%	RR 0.68 (0.59 to 0.78)	3 fewer per 1,000 (from 4 fewer to 2 fewer)	⊕○○○ Very low	NOT IMPORTANT
								4.7%		15 fewer per 1,000 (from 19 fewer to 10 fewer)		

Maternal serious adverse event

Certainty assessment							No of patients		Effect		Certainty	Importance
No of studies	Study design	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Other considerations	therapeutic courses of sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine	no medicine	Relative (95% CI)	Absolute (95% CI)		
8	randomised trials	^d				none	342/6571 (5.2%)		Pooled prevalence 3.84 (2.20 to 5.88)	-- per 1,000 (from -- to --)	-	
Maternal adverse event, IPTp-SP vs placebo or case management												
2	randomised trials	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious ^e	none	25/1981 (1.3%)	27/1360 (2.0%)	RR 0.56 (0.30 to 1.01)	9 fewer per 1,000 (from 14 fewer to 0 fewer)	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate	
Maternal deaths												
6	randomised trials	not serious	not serious	not serious	very serious	none	15/4378 (0.3%)	11/4377 (0.3%)	RR 1.17 (0.49 to 2.80)	0 fewer per 1,000 (from 1 fewer to 5 more)	⊕⊕○○ Low	

CI: confidence interval; MD: mean difference; RR: risk ratio

3.1.1.1 Explanations

- a. Data from surveys may be subject to measurement error and information bias from respondent recall and self-report.
- b. Small numbers, high heterogeneity I^2 79%
- c. Low numbers contributing to outcome. Distinction is not always made between these outcomes in participating studies
- d. No comparison arm
- e. CI crosses the null
- f. Very few events, 95% CI includes both no effect and appreciable risk

4 List of Abbreviations

ACTs	Artemisinin-based combination therapies
AE	Adverse event
AQ	Amodiaquine
AS	Artesunate
CBA	Controlled before-and-after trial
CI	Confidence interval
CQ	Chloroquine
DHPS	Dihydropterote synthase
DP	Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine
G6PD	Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase
HIV	Human immuno-deficiency virus
IPTp	Intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy
ITNs	Insecticide-treated bednets
IRS	Indoor residual spraying
NRCT	Non-randomized controlled trial
NRT	Non-randomized trial
OR	Odds ratio
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
Pf	Plasmodium falciparum
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT	Randomized controlled trial
RR	Risk ratio
RRR	Relative risk reduction
SAE	Serious adverse event
SP	Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine
WHO	World Health Organization

5 Background

Approximately 31 million pregnant women in malaria-endemic regions in Africa were estimated to be at risk of infection with malaria in 2015;¹ no up-to-date estimates are available for regions outside of Africa, but for 2007 the number of malaria exposed pregnancies was estimated to be 94 million.² Malaria in pregnancy is associated with pregnancy loss, preterm birth, low birth weight, fetal growth restriction, and infant and maternal anaemia and clinical illness in the mother.³

Since the 1980s, chemoprevention in pregnancy has been used to reduce the adverse effects of malaria. This consisted initially of chloroquine prophylaxis, but in the 1990s, this was transitioned to intermittent doses of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP); a strategy known as intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy, or IPTp. The WHO guidance for IPTp with SP was first published in 1998. In the Abuja declaration in 2000, leaders of malaria-endemic countries pledged that at least 60% of pregnant women at risk of malaria, especially those in their first pregnancies, would have access to chemoprophylaxis or presumptive treatment.⁴ The guidance for IPTp was updated in 2004 (strategic framework). The most recent version of WHO's IPTp recommendation was released in 2012; the current recommendation states: *"In malaria-endemic areas in Africa, provide intermittent preventive treatment with SP to all women in their first or second pregnancy (SP-IPTp) as part of antenatal care. Dosing should start in the second trimester and doses should be given at least 1 month apart, with the objective of ensuring that at least three doses are received"*.⁵⁻⁷

Although the recommendation only specifies the use of IPTp in the first and second pregnancies, it is standard policy in most malaria-endemic African countries for women to be offered IPTp in all pregnancies. In 2003, Garner and Gulmezoglu published a systematic review including 14 randomised and quasi-randomised malaria chemoprevention trials in pregnancy. They found that regular administration of antimalarials in pregnancy reduced severe maternal anaemia, increased infant birth weight, and likely reduced perinatal mortality, but only showed an effect for women in first and second pregnancies.⁸ In a 2006 update, including 16 randomised or quasi-randomised trials, malaria prophylaxis or IPTp were shown to reduce antenatal parasitemia and placental malaria in all gravidities. However, an effect on birth weight was only found among women in first and second pregnancies.⁹ A subsequent update in 2014 included 17 randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and quasi-RCTs of antimalarials versus placebo or no intervention. This update showed malaria chemoprevention in pregnancy reduced the risk of antenatal and placental parasitemia, maternal anaemia and low birthweight (LBW) among women in their first and second pregnancies (paucigravidae).¹⁰ Chemoprevention was also shown to reduce antenatal parasitemia in women in their third of higher (multigravidae), but there were too few trials to evaluate effects on other outcomes.¹⁰

An analysis of national cross-sectional survey data published in 2012, including 32 surveys from 25 African countries, demonstrated that receipt of at least two doses of IPTp-SP was associated with a statistically significant reduction in LBW, with a similar effect size in pauci-, (20.2%) and multigravidae (21.5%).¹¹

Chico et al. (2015) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis, pairing data from IPTp trials together with data on malaria transmission and prevalence of SP resistance markers, and found that malaria transmission intensity was not correlated with a reduction in the efficacy of IPTp-SP. However, an increase in the prevalence of the highly resistant sextuple mutant, indicated by the presence of >10.1% of the parasite population harbouring the A581G mutation, was associated with reduced SP efficacy.

Given the recognition that more doses of SP might be needed to overcome this increase in resistance, Kayentao et al. (2013) published a meta-analysis of studies comparing two versus three doses of SP to determine whether more doses yielded greater efficacy.¹² This analysis, including data from 7 trials, found that three or more doses of IPTp-SP were associated with significant reductions in maternal and placental parasitemia and higher mean birth weight compared to two doses. The effect was observed among pauci- and multigravidae.¹² Monthly dosing was not associated with an increase in adverse events.¹²

To evaluate further the impact of SP resistance, van Eijk et al. (2019) published a systematic review and meta-analysis on the effect of SP resistance on the effectiveness of IPTp on low birth weight and other outcomes, covering data up to March 2018. Although the effectiveness of IPTp-SP was reduced in high SP resistance areas, it remained associated with reductions in low birth weight even in areas where a substantial proportion of parasites harboured the A581G mutation.¹³

A WHO's evidence review group (ERG) last reviewed the available evidence on the impact of SP resistance of IPTp-SP effectiveness in July 2015. Recommendations were made to the Malaria Policy Action Committee (MPAC) to continue scaling up IPTp-SP, including in high SP resistant areas. The MPAC accepted these recommendations,¹⁴ and no formal revisions to the WHO policy needed to be made.

This current review aims to update to the most review conducted by van Eijk et al. (2019) that assessed the impact of SP resistance on IPTp-SP effectiveness.¹³ It also summarises the evidence on the impact of IPTp-SP by gravidity group and explores the potential modifying effect of malaria transmission intensity on IPTp effectiveness.

6 Objective

To assess the potential modifying effects of gravidity, malaria transmission intensity and SP resistance on the effectiveness of IPTp with SP.

7 Methods

7.1 Eligibility criteria for considering studies for this review

For the quantitative synthesis, we included both randomised and non-randomised studies meeting the following criteria:

7.1.1 Randomised designs

- Individually randomised trials assessing the effects of IPTp vs control OR different numbers of IPTp doses (i.e., ≤2 doses vs 3+ doses)
- Cluster randomised controlled trials (cRCTs) with information on outcomes of interest by the number of SP doses available at the individual level
- Quasi-experimental designs including stepped wedge where sites are randomly allocated with information on outcomes of interest by the number of SP doses

7.1.2 Non-randomised designs

- Cohort studies and surveys after the year 2000 with information on outcomes of interest by the number of SP doses collected at or after delivery

The following studies were excluded:

- case reports and reviews,

- studies where malaria co-interventions (i.e. ITNs, IRS, the standard of care) were not balanced across arms (i.e. the same co-interventions were not available in both arms),
- studies that did not report outcomes of interest by the number of SP doses,
- studies with too little variability in the number of SP doses (e.g. less than 15 women in at least two different SP dose groups),
- studies that combined SP with other drugs such as azithromycin, cotrimoxazole, artemisinins, or amodiaquine.

7.1.3 Types of participants

Pregnant women living in malaria-endemic settings were included, and results were stratified by gravidity 1-2 and 3+ where possible. Studies or study arms involving only HIV-infected women were excluded.

7.1.4 Types of interventions

Intervention: IPTp with SP combined with the standard of care (see below)

Control: The standard of care, defined as malaria case management, combined with insecticide-treated nets or placebo. In the analysis evaluating the effect of 3+ doses of SP, women who received only 0-1 doses of SP (<2012 inclusive) or 0-2 doses (2013 onwards) acted as the control group.

7.1.5 Types of outcome measures

7.1.5.1 *In the mother*

- Anaemia
 - Any anaemia at delivery or in the 3rd trimester: haematocrit <33% or haemoglobin <10 or 11 g/dl as reported by the source study
 - Moderate-severe anaemia at delivery or in the 3rd trimester: Hb <9, <8 or <7 g/dl as reported by the source study
- Malaria at delivery: Peripheral or placental malaria infection detected by microscopy, malaria RDT, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), or histopathology in placental or peripheral maternal blood, regardless of the presence of fever or history of fever
- Peripheral malaria at delivery: Maternal peripheral blood malaria measured at delivery by microscopy, malaria RDT or polymerase chain reaction (PCR), regardless of the presence of fever/ history of fever
- Placental malaria at delivery: Placental malaria detected by any diagnostic test
- Malaria infection during pregnancy: Number of positive smears or RDT positivity regardless of documented fever or history of fever
- Clinical malaria:
 - During pregnancy (incidence): Number of clinical malaria episodes during pregnancy, defined as a positive smear or RDT positivity plus documented fever or history of fever
 - At delivery: Maternal or placental parasitemia at the time of delivery in the presence of a recent history of fever and/or documented fever
- Severe malaria during pregnancy or at delivery, as defined by the study
- Adverse pregnancy outcome:
 - Miscarriage: fetal loss <28 weeks gestation
 - Stillbirth: fetal loss \geq 28 weeks gestation
 - Preterm delivery: delivery <37 weeks gestational age
 - LBW: birth weight < 2,500 gram
- Maternal hospitalisation: hospitalisation during pregnancy because of malaria
- Maternal death: maternal death during pregnancy with malaria as the most likely cause

- Safety: adverse events occurring during pregnancy, such as allergic reactions, nausea, vomiting

7.1.5.2 *In the foetus and infant*

7.1.5.2.1 Primary

- Low birth weight: birthweight <2500 grams

7.1.5.2.2 Secondary

- Parasite prevalence in the cord blood and/or neonatal blood at delivery or infant malaria (symptomatic or asymptomatic) at the time of birth
- Anaemia: cord blood anaemia (Hb<12.5) at delivery
- Severe malaria at birth
- Hospital admission because of malaria at birth
- Death with malaria as the most likely cause in the first year of life

7.2 Search strategy

This review builds on and expands a previously published review by van Eijk, et al.¹³ We searched the following databases using the search terms and strategy described in the Supplement (page 2-3), from March 2018 to September 9, 2021: PubMed/MEDLINE (OVID); EMBASE (OVID); Global Health (OVID); Cochrane Library; CINAHL (EbscoHost); Scopus; and the Malaria in Pregnancy (MIP) Library (<https://mip.wwarn.org/index.php?records&m=search&page=1&ipp=100>) without time or language restrictions

7.3 Data collection and analysis

7.3.1 Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches. The same two reviewers evaluated any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer for full-text eligibility based on pre-determined inclusion criteria. Disagreements were resolved by consensus. Multiple publications from the same study were grouped and included once as a single study at the full-text stage.

7.3.2 Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Any discrepancies in information were resolved by consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. We contacted the study author(s) to retrieve any missing data or for clarifications. Authors of potentially eligible studies with insufficient information for extraction (or with potentially more information than was extractable) were approached by email and sent one reminder. If there was no response, the study was excluded.

Data on study design, study settings (country, location), population characteristics, withdrawal and loss to follow-up, details of the intervention, baseline coverage of malaria co-interventions, number of ANC visits, and outcome data were extracted.

For binary outcomes (Yes/no), we extracted the number of participants with an event (n) and the number of participants (N). For continuous data, we extracted the mean and a measure of variance (e.g. standard deviation) and the number of participants contributing. For the clinical trials, only participants in the IPTp-SP arms were included for the efficacy analysis of the effect of SP by the number of SP doses received. All study arms were included in the analysis of adverse events to allow for comparisons.

Information on latitude and longitude of study locations was obtained for all included studies using Google Earth. The study midyear was calculated, and for studies with no information on study years, we assumed the study was conducted two years before the publication unless the authors provided this information.¹⁵ Using the location and midyear, we assigned each study an indicator of malaria transmission at the time of the study using the *P. falciparum* prevalence among children aged 2-10 years as can be obtained from the Malaria Atlas Project (<https://malariaatlas.org>). Data on the prevalence of *dhps* Ala437Gly, Lys540Glu, and Ala581Gly mutations among *P. falciparum* parasites were extracted from the clinical studies in pregnant women (if provided), and otherwise the literature, or existing molecular surveyor databases (<https://www.wwarn.org/tracking-resistance/sp-molecular-surveyor>). To explore the effect of HIV, we added the prevalence of HIV in the country for the study midyear as obtained from UNAIDS for studies without HIV information from participants. For studies without information on ITN use, we obtained the ITN estimates for the study midyear and location from the Malaria Atlas Project (<https://malariaatlas.org/>).

7.3.3 Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two review team members independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that met eligibility criteria using an adaptation of the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (Supplement).¹⁶ Any discrepancies were resolved through consensus.

7.4 Strategy for data synthesis

7.4.1 Measures of treatment effect

The effect of the intervention was compared using RRs for trend if the outcome was dichotomous or as mean difference for continuous measures. All effects are presented with their 95% confidence intervals.

7.4.2 Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data or supplement available information (e.g., outcomes stratified by gravidity if not available in the publication). No data imputation was applied.

7.4.3 Assessment of heterogeneity

We assessed heterogeneity by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic and Chi^2 test and classified according to the criteria below:

- Moderate: I^2 between 30% and 60%
- Substantial: I^2 values between 50% and 90%
- Considerable: I^2 values between 75% and 100%

Clinical and methodologic explanations for heterogeneity were considered. In addition, meta-regression was used to assess determinants of heterogeneity.

7.4.4 Assessment of reporting biases

Reporting bias was examined using funnel plots for meta-analyses with ten or more studies. Funnel plots were analysed visually and using formal tests for funnel plot asymmetry.¹⁷

7.4.5 Data synthesis

Study-specific endemicity was defined using information from the Malaria Atlas Project (<https://malariaatlas.org/explorer/#/>) matched by time and location of the study ($PfPR_{2-10}$). Initially included studies have been reassigned a value from *Plasmodium falciparum* PR_{2-10} version 2020 for consistency. Malaria endemicity was classified as follows: High: *P. falciparum* prevalence of $\geq 35\%$;

Moderate: *P. falciparum* prevalence of 10-35%; Low: *P. falciparum* prevalence of 0-10%. A very low group (*P. falciparum* <3%) was explored, to assess the usefulness of IPTp in these regions.

Data on the prevalence of *dhps* Ala437Gly, Lys540Glu, and Ala581Gly mutations among *P. falciparum* parasites were extracted from the clinical studies in pregnant women where provided, and otherwise the literature, and the WWARN molecular surveyor database (<http://www.wwarn.org/dhfr-dhps-surveyor/#0>). In areas where the prevalence of *dhps* Lys540Glu was more than 50%, the prevalence of the *dhps* Ala581Gly mutation served as a proxy for the sextuple mutant.

We attempted to match the prevalence of each point mutation for SP resistance markers to each study as in the previous study by time (within 3 years before or after for point mutations) and by location using latitude and longitude (within 300 km).¹⁸ A score was assigned to each match, based on the time between the study on SP resistance marker and the clinical study, the distance between location of SP resistance marker assessment and the clinical study and the overall sample size (≥ 30 yes/no) for SP resistance marker, with a maximum score of three points.

All summary estimates from the studies identified in the literature were combined to perform an aggregated level meta-analysis using Stata version 17. A two-stage random-effects meta-analysis was performed using weighted mixed-effects models for nonlinear trend estimation of summarised dose-response data.¹⁹⁻²¹ This 2-stage method allowed us to combine the study-specific slopes from studies that reported risk for different groupings (i.e., 0 vs 2+ SP doses, 0, 1, 2 or 0, 1, 2+ doses, etc.). A single summary estimate for the effect per dose per study was computed using the correlated log RR estimates or means across SP dose categories (step 1). These were then combined across studies using random-effects meta-analysis, with heterogeneity quantified using the I^2 statistic (step 2).^{19,20,22} Results were expressed as mean difference (inverse variance) or relative risk reduction [RRR]: $RRR; 100 \times [1 - \text{relative risk}]$ (Mantel-Haenszel) per dose-step increase.

A range of combinations of threshold levels (at 5% or 10% step increases) of the resistance-associated mutations in *dhps* were explored to define SP resistance area into low, medium, high and very high SP resistance. This was conducted using the aggregated data and any malaria at delivery (placental or maternal malaria detected by any diagnostic test) as the outcome measure of interest. Because of distinct parasite populations and distributions of mutations in each region,^{1,23} threshold analyses were done separately for central and west Africa and east and southern Africa. Results were then combined to obtain a single categorical variable that represented the optimal thresholds based on the p-value and tau². The most optimal definition for SP-resistance that was obtained was as follows: Low SP resistance: Ala437Gly <75% (Central/West Africa) or Lys540Glu <40% (East/southern Africa); Moderate: Ala437Gly $\geq 75\%$ (Central/West Africa) or Lys540Glu 40-60% & AlaA581Gly <5% (East/southern Africa); High: Lys540Glu ≥ 60 & Ala581Gly <5% (East/Southern Africa), and very high resistance: Lys540Glu ≥ 60 & Ala581Gly $\geq 5\%$ (East/Southern Africa).

Multivariate meta-regression was used to explore the potential modifying effect of SP resistance and malaria transmission intensity (PfPR₂₋₁₀), with the number of SP doses received, malaria transmission, HIV infection, and percentage of paucigravidae (in the models including all gravidae), study quality score and ITN coverage as co-variables. ITN was only included when it was significant in univariate analyses; all other variables were maintained in multivariate analyses to allow comparisons.

Outcomes such as the effect of IPTp doses on the infant were scarce, and these were described where available. We used P values of <0.05 to indicate statistical significance (2-sided tests).

7.4.6 Subgroup analysis

All main outcomes were examined by gravidity. The effects of malaria transmission and parasite resistance were examined in meta-regression and in a separate analysis for $PfPR_{2-10} < 3\%$.

7.4.7 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis was performed by excluding low-quality studies and studies without optimal matching for the *dhps* resistance markers involved. Publication and small-study bias were assessed by visual inspection of funnel plots and Egger's test for small-study effects (Figure S6).

7.4.8 Adverse event analysis

The prevalence of adverse events was recorded by study arm for all trials with an IPTp-SP arm. The pooled prevalence was obtained using metaprop in Stata for adverse events that were reported in at least six or more reports. Because of the high heterogeneity, the median and range were additionally assessed. The risk ratios of adverse events comparing IPTp arms and alternative arms were calculated and presented in the forest plots. For studies with more than one comparison arm, the results in the IPTp-SP arm were split so that a comparison could be made with each alternative arm. If there were a sufficient number of studies that used a placebo or case-management arm for an outcome, the risk ratios were pooled using random-effects meta-analysis.

7.4.9 Certainty of the evidence

Where randomised trials were analysed according to study arm, they start at a high certainty of evidence, but they could be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. When data from randomised trials were analysed in a manner that differed from the original randomisation, we considered them as starting at low certainty of evidence but allowed for upgrading based on the same criteria as non-randomised studies. Non-randomised studies started at a low certainty of evidence but could be upgraded if there was a large or a dose-response effect and if all plausible residual confounding would have reduced a demonstrated effect or would have suggested a spurious effect if no effect was observed²⁴. The certainty of evidence and results are summarised in the summary of findings tables²⁵⁻²⁷.

The certainty of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach,²⁵ and each outcome was rated as described by Balshem et al. as follows.^{24,25}

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

8 Results

8.1 Results of the search

Through database searching, 3,057 records were identified. These were assessed for eligibility, and 102 with one or more outcomes were included in the review: 7 trials comparing IPTp-SP against placebo or passive case detection, 12 trials or cohorts following women who received IPTp-SP, and 83 observational studies (Figure 1). A summary and a map of the location of the included studies are

provided in the supplement (Figure S1, Table S1). More studies were situated in central and west Africa (59.3%) than in east and southern Africa (40.7%); the time period stretched from 1993 to 2020. The majority of studies were of moderate-to-low quality (74.4%).

8.1.1 Analysis of protection per dose of SP

8.1.1.1 *Maternal malaria infection at the time of delivery*

The pooled relative risk reduction per dose of SP for malaria infection was 20% (15-25%) overall (RR=0.80, 95% CI 0.75-0.85). There was a clear trend toward reducing efficacy with increase resistance. The RRR reduced from 28% (95% CI 20-36) in the lowest resistance strata to 22% (14-29), 8% (0-7), and -5% (-16, 5) in the moderate, high, and very high resistance strata, respectively (Figure 2), defined as *Pfdhps*-A437G <75% (Central/West Africa) or *Pfdhs*-K540E <40% (East/Southern Africa) for low resistance, *Pfdhps*-A437G ≥75% (Central/West Africa) or *Pfdhs*-K540E 40-60% (East/Southern Africa) for moderate resistance, *Pfdhps*-K540E ≥60% and *Pfdhps*-A581G <5% (East/Southern Africa) for high resistance, and *Pfdhps*-K540E ≥60% and *Pfdhps*-A581G ≥5% (East/Southern Africa) for very-high resistance. Multivariate meta-regression showed that the prevalence of *dhps* Lys540Glu in the study area significantly affected the log risk ratio for SP dose as shown by the upward slope of the regression line which indicated a decrease in the effectiveness of SP with increasing occurrence of this resistance marker ($p=0.003$, Figure 3, left panel). The trend for decreasing effectiveness with increasing SP resistance was significant for all gravidae and paucigravidae, but not for multigravidae, in univariate and multivariate analyses (see Table 1 note). Malaria transmission ($PfPR_{2-10}$) did not affect the effectiveness of SP for reducing maternal malaria, as shown by the horizontal line in Figure 3 (right panel).

Similar patterns were seen when evaluating placental malaria and malaria infections by any test in any compartment for all gravidae combined (Figure S3-5) and primigravidae. IPTp-SP was also associated with significant relative risk reductions for cord blood malaria with an overall RRR of 19% (95% CI 12-26%, I^2 0%, 20 studies) per dose of SP, but the trend by SP resistance was not significant ($p=0.24$).

8.1.1.2 *Maternal anaemia and haemoglobin*

IPTp-SP was associated with an increase of 0.19 g/dl in haemoglobin among all gravidae (95% CI 0.15-0.22; I^2 1%, 46 studies). Although there was a significant trend towards decreasing efficacy with increasing SP resistance (Table S5), the protective effect remained evident in the highest resistance strata (mean difference 0.18 g/dL, 95% CI 0.11-0.25, $I^2=0$, $P<0.0001$). Similarly, each dose of IPTp was associated with 10% relative risk reduction in anaemia (95% CI 8-13%; I^2 70%, 53 studies, Table 1), and the effect remained statistically significant in the highest resistance strata (RRR=8%, 95% CI 3-13, $I^2=0$, 5 studies) (Table 1, Figure 4).

8.1.1.3 *Birthweight*

IPTp was also associated with a relative risk reduction for low birth weight of 25% (95% CI 22–29%; ($I^2=71%$, 98 studies, Table 1) per dose of SP. This was 26% (21–31%, $I^2=62%$; 59 studies) in paucigravidae, and 21% (16–26%, $I^2=45%$, 49 studies) in multigravidae (Table 1). Although a decreasing effect with increasing SP resistance was noted (Figure 5, Figure 6), this trend was not statistically significant overall (p for SP resistance trend 0.08) or by gravidity (Table 1) or in univariate or multivariate meta-regression (Table S5). In the very-high SP resistance category, IPTp-SP was associated with a non-significant 16% (-4, 32) reduction in LBW ($I^2=69%$, 6 studies).

Each dose of IPTp-SP was also associated with a 57 grams increase in mean birth weight among the all gravidae group (95% CI 44-69 grams, I^2 56%, 82 studies). This was 67 grams in paucigravidae (95% CI 50-85 grams, I^2 44%, 62 studies) and 43g in multigravidae (95% CI 26-60 grams, I^2 47%, 45 studies)

(Table 1). Significant benefits of IPTp on mean birthweight were noted in all but the highest SP resistance category. The mean difference in birth weight was 65 grams (95% CI 44- 87), 66 grams (95% CI 45-88), 46 grams (95% CI 27-66) in the lowest, middle, and high SP resistance areas, with a non-significant mean difference of 11 gm (95% CI -9-32 gm) in the highest resistance areas (Table 1, Figures S5 and S6). Multivariate meta-regression among all gravidae showed that for each increase in SP resistance level, a reduction of 16 grams (95% CI 4-29) in the effect of IPTp-SP on mean birth weight was seen. This reflected a trend among paucigravidae only (25g [8-41]), and not among multigravidae (2g [-15 to 19]) (Table S5). Significant increases in mean birthweight associated with IPTp-SP were seen in all resistance strata, except the very-high resistance category (11g, 95% CI -9, 32), $I^2=17\%$, 7 studies)

8.1.1.4 Preterm delivery

Although included here, it should be noted that the evaluation of preterm delivery and number of SP doses is problematic, given that prematurity inherently reduces the opportunity to receive more SP doses. Overall, per dose of SP, IPTp was associated with an RRR for prematurity of 24% (95% CI 19–29; I^2 77%, 59 studies; Table 1); this was 28% (95% CI 21-34%, I^2 69%, 40 studies) among paucigravidae, and 20% (95% CI 12-27%, I^2 56%, 31 studies) in multigravidae. The reduction in preterm births was significant in all but the highest SP resistance level. Multivariate meta-regression analyses showed a linear trend towards decreasing effectiveness of SP with increasing SP resistance for all gravidae and primigravidae, but not multigravidae, but the effect was not significant ($p=0.07$, Table 1).

8.1.1.5 Stillbirths

IPTp-SP was associated with a 30% reduction in stillbirth per dose (95% CI 17-41%, I^2 80%, $n=44$, Table 2). The RRR decreased with increasing level of SP resistance, but this trend was not significant in univariate or multivariate meta-regression (Table S5). Among women who received IPTp-SP (30 comparisons, 17,998 women) there was a pooled prevalence of stillbirth of 2.03 (95% CI 1.66-2.44, $p<0.0001$, I^2 61.6). There was no significant difference in the risk of stillbirth among women who received IPTp-SP (113/4789) versus placebo or case-management (94/4380; pooled risk ratio 1.07, 95% CI 0.82-1.41, $p=0.62$, I^2 0%) (Figure S9).

8.1.1.6 Other outcomes examined with a limited number of studies

There were nine studies that reported on foetal anaemia (defined per individual studies as a cord haemoglobin <14 or <12.5 g/dl), with an RRR per dose of SP of 8% (95% CI -2 to 18%, I^2 63.1%). Clinical malaria, defined as one or more episodes of malaria during follow up in pregnancy, was reported by nine studies, with an RRR of 25% (95% CI 8 to 39%) per dose of IPTp-SP but high heterogeneity (I^2 93%, Table 2). Benefits per SP dose were additionally noted for cord haemoglobin, newborn head circumference and length, and maternal postpartum haemorrhage, but not for pre-eclampsia (Table 2). Maternal IPTp use was a protective factor for infant malaria in a study in Benin, a risk factor in a study in Cameroon,²⁸ and not associated with infant malaria in a study in Ghana (Table S6).²⁹

8.1.2 Subgroup analysis: low transmission areas

Five studies were conducted in areas with a PfPR₂₋₁₀ $< 3\%$: two in Senegal and one each in Uganda, Tanzania, and Sudan. Results for dichotomous outcomes that were available across studies (LBW, maternal malaria, placental malaria, maternal anaemia) are shown in Figure 7. Although some individual studies in low transmission areas showed a protective effect of IPTp-SP, overall, the protective effect of IPTp-SP was not statistically significant for any outcome except for anaemia (two studies, I^2 0%; 0.91, 95% CI 0.85-0.97). The study conducted in the area with the lowest transmission (Ndyomugenyi et al., 2011) did not show a protective effect for any outcome presented.³⁰ This study was conducted in an area of high SP resistance and under high ITN coverage.³⁰ When removing this study, IPTp was protective for low birth weight (RR per dose 0.76, 95% CI 0.60-0.95, $n=5$, $I^2=64\%$) and

maternal malaria (RR per dose 0.61, 95% CI 0.42-0.81, $I^2=68\%$, $n=3$), and associated with an increased mean birth weight (mean difference per SP dose 150 grams, 95% CI 29-271 grams, $I^2=83\%$, $n=3$). For placental malaria, the RR per dose was 0.78, 95% CI 0.59-1.03 ($n=2$, $I^2=0\%$), and for maternal anaemia it was 0.90 (95% CI 0.83-0.98, $n=1$).

8.1.3 Sensitivity analysis

Results were generally similar when excluding low-quality studies or when only including studies with good matching for SP resistance markers (Table S3). There was evidence for publication and small sample bias for the outcome of low birth weight, maternal anaemia, and preterm delivery, but not for other outcomes (Figure S8).

8.1.4 Adverse events

Thirty trials with 71 arms and at least one IPTp-SP arm had information on adverse events (characteristics in Table S7); one trial (Kajubi et al.) provided women with a mean of 5.25 doses of IPTp-SP with 162 women receiving 6 and 67 receiving 7 doses.³¹ Including these women, across the randomized controlled trials where information was available, at least 1041 women received 4 doses, 244 received 5 doses, 192 received 6 doses of IPTp-SP, and 67 receiving 7 doses. The reported prevalence of most adverse events was low and within the range of the comparison arms (Table 3; Forest plots S9-S18). The pooled prevalence of serious adverse events and adverse events among IPTp-SP recipients was 3.84% (95% CI 2.20-5.88, 8 trials, 6571 participants) and 14.3% (95% CI 4.9-27.5%) (16 trials, 8122 participants), respectively. In two trials comparing IPTp-SP vs placebo or case-management, the pooled risk ratio of an adverse event was 0.56 (95% CI 0.30-1.01) in favour of IPTp-SP. Skin reactions were rarely reported, with a pooled prevalence of 0.4% (95% CI 0.2-0.7) among women in IPTp-SP arms (11 trials, 4186 participants), with no significant increase seen in the two trials comparing IPTp-SP with placebo/ case management (pooled RR 1.24, 95% CI 0.34-4.58). For a limited number of outcomes, enough data was available to compare an IPTp-SP arm with a placebo or case-management arm (Table 4). No difference was seen between these arms for any safety outcomes examined.

9 Discussion

Despite increasing resistance to SP, this review highlights that IPTp-SP continues to benefit pregnant women of all gravidities and their infants. However, there is a clear trend toward reduced effectiveness of IPTp-SP to treat and prevent malaria infections with increasing resistance. While IPTp-SP had no impact on malaria infections in areas with the highest level of SP resistance, defined by a prevalence of 5% or more of the *Pfdhps*-A581G mutation in the presence of at least 60% *Pfdhps*-K540E, it remained associated with significant increases in mean haemoglobin and related reductions in maternal anaemia. Albeit smaller than in low-resistance areas and not statistically significant, the direction of effect for LBW in these very high resistant areas also suggested a potential beneficial impact in favour of IPTp-SP. However, the number of studies contributing to the LBW analysis in these highest resistance areas was limited to six, and there was substantial heterogeneity between studies.

This analysis builds on the previous meta-analysis,³² and adds 36 studies involving 29,059 participants. It confirms that despite a near-complete loss of its antimalarial effects in very high SP resistant areas, SP continues to positively impact fetal growth and maternal anaemia. It has been hypothesised that this is mediated through the non-malarial properties of SP.³³ This is consistent with the results of a recent IPD meta-analysis of six trials comparing IPTp with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) vs SP. This showed that IPTp with DP is much more effective in high SP resistant areas than SP in reducing malaria, preventing about two out of every three infections relative to SP. However, this did not translate into better pregnancy outcomes, primarily because SP was associated with better fetal

growth, resulting in higher mean birthweights in all gravaidae groups. This was seen even though the infants in the IPTp-SP arms were born to mothers who had 60% to 70% more infections than mothers in the DP arms. These non-malaria effects of SP require further elucidation. The results of these recently completed IPTp trials suggest that SP's non-malarial effect may be mediated, at least in part, through better gestational weight gain in the mother (Gutman et al., personal communications, Madanitsa et al., personal communications). This may reflect the broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties of sulfadoxine, a long-acting sulphonamide and the associated reduced risk for persistent bacterial infections and/or could reflect its influence on the maternal gut microbiome or ability to reduce inflammation.³³⁻³⁵

Although the benefits of IPTp-SP in paucigravaidae have been well documented, the benefits for multigravaidae have been less well defined.⁹ Early placebo-controlled trials mainly included paucigravaidae,³⁶⁻³⁹ whereas the later trials that included multigravaidae evaluated the effect of IPTp-SP when most women were also issued ITNs.^{30,40,41} This review demonstrated the beneficial impact of IPTp among multigravaidae on birth weight and maternal anaemia. The effect sizes were generally smaller than in paucigravaidae, likely reflecting the smaller attributable fraction of malaria in multigravaidae. Other contributing factors such as nutritional deficiencies may be relatively more important in multigravaidae.⁴²

It remains a question whether there continues to be a role for IPTp in areas where malaria transmission has fallen to low levels due to scale-up of malaria control and elimination efforts or environmental changes. A prior review did not identify studies in low transmission areas.⁴³ There was some suggestion that IPTp-SP increases birth weight and haemoglobin concentrations even in areas with very low malaria transmission, defined in our study as a $PfPR_{2-10} < 3\%$. The non-malarial effect of SP may partly contribute to this.

Some studies reported on other infant growth parameters, such as newborn head circumference and length (Table 2), and these improved with IPTp, as may be expected. Placental malaria and maternal anaemia have been associated with blood loss at delivery. This may provide a mechanism for the association seen between the reduction in maternal postpartum haemorrhage and IPTp, reported in three studies.^{44,45} We tried to identify reports on the effects of IPTp-SP on the risk of malaria in the infant. However, there were insufficient data available in a format that could be used for the analysis (Table S6). The limited results were contradictory, and further study is warranted (Table S6).

This study has several limitations. We used the dose-response of IPTp-SP as a proxy marker of efficacy. However, observational studies are prone to bias. For example, women who receive a relatively high number of IPTp doses are likely to differ from those that received no or an inadequate number of doses of IPTp-SP. They may differ in age, gravidity, distance to the nearest health facility providing antenatal care, or in the means to visit the ANC regularly. Although multivariate meta-regression will have reduced the potential for bias, residual confounding is likely because only study-level co-variables were available in this aggregated data meta-analysis. For some studies, time and space-matched local resistance data were not available and were obtained from other sources, which are less precise. Some studies were considered of poor quality with a trend towards greater effectiveness with decreasing study quality. Still, sensitivity analysis showed that these were equally distributed across the resistance spectrum and did not impact the conclusions. Similarly, there was evidence of a small-study effect, primarily for low birthweight, but this was also observed in all resistance strata. In addition, the meta-analysis suffered from design and reporting variation and small numbers in the extreme dose groups (0-dose and 3+ doses). This was partly mitigated by using a dose-response analysis that placed less emphasis on the extreme dose groups.

The strength of this review includes a large number of studies and participants and the use of a novel method to estimate nonlinear dose-response relationship in meta-analyses,²¹ as opposed to the linear dose-response used in the previous meta-analysis.

9.1 Conclusion

This review builds upon prior evidence demonstrating that IPTp-SP is beneficial to both paucigravid and multigravid pregnant women in sub-Saharan Africa. We confirm a clear relationship between the degree of SP resistance in the prevailing parasite population and the effectiveness of IPTp on clinical outcomes. However, even in areas where SP's ability to clear existing infections or prevent new ones is severely compromised, IPTp-SP continues to confer a clinical benefit on fetal growth and maternal haemoglobin levels, albeit less than in low SP resistance areas. This resilient effect of SP may reflect a potent non-malarial effect of SP, which requires further elucidation. IPTp-SP should continue to be used in high SP resistant areas until more effective alternatives for malaria chemoprevention are found. Further IPTp trials are needed to explore the combination of SP plus dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine in high SP resistance areas to explore the combined benefits of the superior antimalarial efficacy of DP and the potent non-malarial effects of SP on fetal growth.

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11 Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

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13 Figures

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram

Search terms: "Malaria AND pregnan AND intermittent AND (prevent* OR prophyla* OR presumpt* OR chemoprevent* OR chemoprophyla* OR IPT*) AND (sulfadoxine OR sulphadoxine OR pyrimethamine OR SP)"

Figure 2: Forest plot of the relative risk of maternal malaria infection associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp in all gravidae by SP resistance strata

Figure 3: Correlation between relative risk for maternal malaria infection in women receiving IPTp and the prevalence of *dhps* Lys540Glu mutations and PfPR₂₋₁₀

71 studies, adjusted R^2 25%.
 Meta-regression coefficient: 0.0027, 95% CI 0.0010, 0.0045, $p=0.003$ (for linear trend)

Meta-regression bubble plots show the log of the relative risk estimates for maternal malaria across each sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine dose category, obtained by use of generalised least-squares regression for trend estimation of summarised dose-response data. The size of the bubbles for individual studies is proportional to the sample size. A positive slope indicates decreasing effectiveness of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp for averting maternal malaria with increasing mutation prevalence. *dhps*=dihydropteroate synthase. IPTp=intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy

PfPR₂₋₁₀: *P. falciparum* parasite prevalence in children aged 2-10 years as obtained for the year of study and study locations from the Malaria Atlas Project (<https://malariaatlas.org>)
 72 studies, Adjusted R^2 0.0%. Meta-regression coefficient 0.0001, 95% CI -0.0043, 0.0045, $p=0.960$ (for linear trend)

Figure 4: Forest plot of the relative risk of anaemia (haemoglobin < 11 g/dl) associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp by resistance strata

P-values following the I^2 statistics represent the χ^2 test for heterogeneity. Weights are from random-effects analysis. Data marker sizes indicate the weight applied to each study using random-effects meta-analysis. Diamonds represent summary effect of studies. *dhps*=dihydropteroate synthase. D+L=Dersimonian-Laird method for random-effects models. IPTp=intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy. IV=inverse variance method for fixed-effects models. SP; sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine
 Note: Reference refers to the lowest sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine dose category (0 or 0–1 dose as indicated in the sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine dose category column), and the comparison column (included for illustration only) refers to all the other exposure groups pooled (e.g., if the sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine categories were 0, 1, 2+, the comparison column would reflect the data in the 1 dose group and 2+ dose groups pooled)

Figure 5: Forest plot of the relative risk of low birth weight associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp in low and moderate SP resistance areas

Figure 6: Forest plot of the relative risk of low birthweight associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPTp in high and super SP resistance areas

P-values following the I^2 statistics represent the χ^2 test for heterogeneity. Weights are from random-effects analysis. Data marker sizes indicate the weight applied to each study using random-effects meta-analysis. Diamonds represent summary effect of studies. *dhps*=dihydropteroate synthase. D+L=Dersimonian-Laird method for random-effects models. IPTp=intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy. IV=inverse variance method for fixed-effects models. SP; sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine

Note: Reference refers to the lowest sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine dose category (0 or 0–1 dose as indicated in the sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine dose category column), and the comparison column (included for illustration only) refers to all the other exposure groups pooled (e.g., if the sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine categories were 0, 1, 2+, the comparison column would reflect the data in the 1 dose group and 2+ dose groups pooled)

Figure 7: Forest plot of the relative risk of several outcomes associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine IPT in areas of low malaria transmission (*Pf*PR2-10 < 3%, all gravidae), Africa 1993-2020

NOTE: Weights are from random effects analysis

14 Tables

Table 1: Relative risk reduction and mean difference for several outcomes associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine by resistance level, overall and by gravidity, 1997-2020

Outcome and resistance category*	All gravidae					Paucigravidae					Multigravidae				
	Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled protective effectiveness [†] % Relative Risk Reduction (RRR) (95% CI)	P‡	I ² , %	Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled protective effectiveness [†] % Relative Risk Reduction (RRR) (95% CI)	P‡	I ² , %	Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled protective effectiveness [†] % Relative Risk Reduction (RRR) (95% CI)	P‡	I ² , %
Low birth weight															
All studies	98	80,519	25.3 (21.8, 28.7)	<.0001	70.8	59	22,232	26.4 (21.4, 31.0)	<.0001	61.5	49	27,663	21.0 (15.6, 26.1)	<.0001	44.7
Low resistance	40	27,130	28.4 (22.7, 33.7)	<.0001	68.7	28	11,217	30.3 (23.3, 36.7)	<.0001	58.3	19	9454	26.1 (14.8, 35.9)	<.0001	56.2
Moderate resistance	29	31,233	25.6 (18.8, 31.9)	<.0001	75.6	10	2364	20.3 (10.1, 29.3)	0.0002	46.6	10	7189	18.9 (8.8, 27.8)	0.0004	52.7
High resistance	23	15,777	22.6 (15.6, 29.0)	<.0001	58.9	15	6070	26.0 (15.8, 35.0)	<.0001	67.4	14	7258	21.7 (13.3, 29.3)	<.0001	15.2
Very-high resistance	6	6379	16.1 (-3.8, 32.2)	0.11	61.9	6	2581	23.7 (-11.8, 47.9)	0.17	70.9	6	3762	11.2 (-6.6, 26.0)	0.20	16.5
Maternal anaemia (<11 g/dl)															
All studies	53	38,727	10.3 (7.5, 12.9)	<.0001	70.2	32	16,327	10.1 (5.7, 14.2)	<.0001	72.3	22	10,829	7.7 (4.0, 11.3)	<.0001	39.8
Low resistance	15	8844	12.6 (5.9, 18.7)	0.0003	62.3	13	5943	13.8 (6.8, 20.3)	0.0002	47.9	5	1370	-3.8 (-20.3, 10.4)	0.62	27.1
Moderate resistance	15	9028	16.9 (10.4, 23.0)	<.0001	83.2	4	1107	16.2 (3.7, 27.2)	0.0131	60.9	4	3189	12.5 (2.5, 21.4)	0.0154	83.6
High resistance	18	16,630	5.7 (2.0, 9.3)	0.0026	53.8	11	8095	6.6 (-1.6, 14.1)	0.11	81.9	9	5091	5.8 (1.7, 9.7)	0.0056	0.0
Very-high resistance	5	4225	8.2 (2.6, 13.4)	0.0046	0.0	4	1182	7.8 (-1.3, 16.2)	0.09	0.0	4	1179	10.2 (0.9, 18.6)	0.0331	0.0
Maternal moderate anaemia **															
All studies	28	25,211	26.7 (18.5, 34.0)	<.0001	51.1	21	13,785	22.9 (12.7, 32.0)	<.0001	31.1	16	11229	24.3 (10.5, 35.9)	0.0011	38.0
Low resistance	13	9378	31.2 (16.0, 43.6)	0.0002	68.8	9	5040	29.2 (9.5, 44.6)	0.0059	42.0	4	2962	13.9 (-147.9, 70.1)	0.78	62.3
Moderate resistance	1	1277	40.5 (22.3, 54.4)	0.0001	-	1	320	67.5 (30.2, 84.9)	0.0040	-	1	950	32.5 (7.7, 50.6)	0.0137	-
High resistance	12	13083	20.2 (11.2, 28.2)	<.0001	0.0	9	7577	15.0 (1.8, 26.3)	0.0268	1.5	9	6542	20.0 (6.8, 31.3)	0.0042	0.0
Very-high resistance	2	1473	6.0 (-18.4, 25.4)	0.60	0.0	2	848	22.8 (-12.1, 46.8)	0.17	6.9	2	775	-6.6 (-74.2, 34.7)	0.80	8.9
Any malaria infection§															
All studies	94	53,921	20.2 (16.0, 24.1)	<.0001	74.0	53	19,552	24.4 (19.3, 29.3)	<.0001	58.5	41	19,478	16.9 (13.0, 20.6)	<.0001	0.0

Low resistance	35	21,934	27.1 (20.5, 33.2)	<.0001	74.0	¶	28	10,403	29.7 (21.7, 36.8)	<.0001	68.4	¶	18	8004	18.1 (10.9, 24.7)	<.0001	10.3
Moderate resistance	30	12,455	21.3 (14.2, 27.8)	<.0001	70.0		6	1852	26.8 (21.7, 31.6)	<.0001	0.0		6	3782	16.9 (10.4, 22.9)	<.0001	0.4
High resistance	23	15,324	8.7 (2.9, 14.2)	0.0037	27.2		16	6364	17.2 (9.4, 24.3)	<.0001	19.4		14	6746	13.8 (5.0, 21.8)	0.0027	0.0
Very-high resistance	6	4208	-1.2 (-12.5, 8.9)	0.82	19.6		3	933	3.4 (-17.9, 20.9)	0.73	3.9		3	946	10.8 (-35.4, 41.3)	0.59	24.3
Maternal peripheral malaria infection (any test)																	
All studies	72	49,826	20.4 (15.3, 25.2)	<.0001	73.3		44	19,952	23.3 (16.5, 29.6)	<.0001	69.0		34	17,252	13.7 (7.2, 19.6)	<.0001	24.2
Low resistance	29	17,408	28.4 (20.4, 35.6)	<.0001	77.7	¶	24	8964	27.9 (18.2, 36.5)	<.0001	74.8	¶	15	6315	13.4 (3.4, 22.3)	0.0100	28.8
Moderate resistance	21	10,563	21.6 (13.8, 28.7)	<.0001	53.5		4	1185	26.1 (17.4, 34.0)	<.0001	0.0		4	3406	15.6 (8.6, 22.1)	<.0001	0.0
High resistance	18	16,773	8.5 (-0.3, 16.5)	0.06	41.6		13	8681	13.0 (4.0, 21.1)	0.0055	26.9		12	6368	10.6 (-6.7, 25.0)	0.21	44.1
Very-high resistance	4	5082	-5.0 (-15.6, 4.7)	0.32	0.0		3	1122	2.2 (-22.1, 21.7)	0.84	0.0		3	1163	-1.3 (-64.5, 37.6)	0.96	0.0
Placental malaria infection (any test)																	
All studies	76	41,884	21.6 (16.5, 26.5)	<.0001	72.8		43	17,277	25.4 (19.5, 30.9)	<.0001	61.8		30	11,464	18.8 (11.7, 25.4)	<.0001	0.0
Low resistance	31	18,616	25.7 (17.7, 32.9)	<.0001	75.3	¶	25	9470	31.1 (22.8, 38.5)	<.0001	68.0	¶	14	4388	11.9 (-1.4, 23.4)	0.08	17.0
Moderate resistance	22	9094	23.4 (13.7, 32.1)	<.0001	74.2		3	1257	27.2 (20.8, 33.0)	<.0001	0.0		3	2466	31.1 (17.5, 42.4)	<.0001	0.0
High resistance	18	10,877	17.2 (11.7, 22.5)	<.0001	0.0		12	5637	17.4 (8.3, 25.7)	0.0004	25.1		10	3700	16.0 (0.7, 29.0)	0.0406	0.0
Very-high resistance	5	3297	-6.8 (-16.1, 1.8)	0.12	0.0		3	913	2.4 (-18.9, 20.0)	0.81	0.0		3	910	32.2 (2.5, 52.9)	0.0363	0.0
Preterm delivery																	
All studies	59	37,848	24.0 (19.1, 28.6)	<.0001	77.0		40	16,086	27.5 (20.5, 33.8)	<.0001	69.3		31	12,855	20.0 (12.1, 27.3)	<.0001	55.7
Low resistance	21	11,622	37.4 (25.8, 47.2)	<.0001	82.3		19	6325	38.5 (24.3, 50.1)	<.0001	73.3		12	3674	22.3 (-2.7, 41.2)	0.08	61.3
Moderate resistance	18	8311	18.8 (11.9, 25.2)	<.0001	62.3		6	1206	25.0 (10.0, 37.4)	0.0020	31.5		6	3100	20.0 (12.0, 27.4)	<.0001	0.0
High resistance	17	15,438	24.4 (15.2, 32.7)	<.0001	80.1		13	7816	24.7 (14.6, 33.5)	<.0001	74.3		11	5348	20.8 (9.0, 31.2)	0.0010	66.7
Very-high resistance	3	2437	3.0 (-13.6, 17.2)	0.70	0.0		2	739	2.8 (-35.1, 30.1)	0.86	0.0		2	733	10.1 (-45.7, 44.5)	0.67	22.1
Continuous variables	Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled weighted mean difference (95% CI) per incremental dose	P‡	I², %		Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled weighted mean difference (95% CI) per incremental dose	P‡	I², %		Number of studies	Number of women	Pooled weighted mean difference (95% CI) per incremental dose	P‡	I², %
Maternal haemoglobin (g/dl)																	
All studies	46	30,809	0.19 (0.15, 0.22)	<.0001	1.1		32	14,520	0.18 (0.10, 0.27)	<.0001	46.0		22	8589	0.17 (0.09, 0.26)	<.0001	6.5
Low resistance	19	11,098	0.28 (0.17, 0.38)	<.0001	31.0	¶	17	6590	0.32 (0.18, 0.45)	<.0001	26.3	¶	9	2790	0.31 (0.16, 0.46)	<.0001	0.0
Moderate resistance	8	3338	0.29 (0.18, 0.39)	<.0001	0.0		4	453	0.33 (-0.08, 0.74)	0.11	0.0		3	1186	0.28 (0.03, 0.54)	0.0272	0.0

High resistance	12	11764	0.11 (0.04, 0.18)	0.0015	0.0	9	6999	0.06 (-0.04, 0.16)	0.22	42.8	7	3587	0.02 (-0.11, 0.14)	0.78	2.3
Very-high resistance	5	4609	0.18 (0.11, 0.25)	<.0001	0.0	2	478	0.15 (0.05, 0.25)	0.0026	0.0	3	1026	0.24 (0.10, 0.37)	0.0004	0.0
Birthweight (grams)															
All studies	82	55,625	56.5 (44.3, 68.6)	<.0001	55.5	62	22,895	67.1 (49.7, 84.6)	<.0001	43.9	45	20,961	43.1 (26.2, 60.1)	<.0001	46.5
Low resistance	29	17,422	65.4 (44.2, 86.5)	<.0001	35.3 ¶	25	10,390	82.6 (55.6, 109.7)	<.0001	34.3 ¶	14	4734	39.1 (11.0, 67.2)	0.0065	17.4
Moderate resistance	27	17,891	66.4 (45.1, 87.6)	<.0001	58.0	16	3235	91.7 (59.6, 123.8)	<.0001	6.6	13	6947	58.5 (25.4, 91.6)	0.0005	39.3
High resistance	19	13,694	46.5 (27.2, 65.7)	<.0001	39.9	14	6689	58.7 (32.1, 85.2)	<.0001	29.9	12	5517	45.1 (16.2, 74.1)	0.0022	46.8
Very-high resistance	7	6618	11.4 (-9.3, 32.1)	0.28	17.4	7	2581	7.6 (-24.9, 40.1)	0.65	23.3	6	3763	22.1 (-30.9, 75.0)	0.41	65.6

* SP resistance definition based on outcome in univariate meta-regression for any malaria at the time of delivery (lowest p-value and tau² of evaluation of definitions using stepwise incrementation of *dhps* Ala437Gly, Lys540Glu and Ala581Gly): Low: *Pfdhps*-A437G <75% (Central/West Africa) or Lys540Glu <40% (East/southern Africa); Moderate: *Pfdhps*-A437G ≥75% (Central/West Africa) or Lys540Glu 40-60% & Ala581Gly <5% (East/southern Africa); High: Lys540Glu ≥60 & Ala581Gly <5% (East/southern Africa); Very-high: Lys540Glu ≥60 & Ala581Gly ≥5% (East/southern Africa).

†Pooled effect per incremental SP dose obtained by meta-analysis; ‡ P-value for Z-test that the risk reduction or the weighted mean difference is 0; § Any malaria infection at delivery (maternal or placental blood) by any test

¶ P-value for trend of SP resistance levels <0.05, univariate analyses. P-values for trend in univariate analyses were as follows: Any malaria: all gravities p=0.0004, paucigravidae p=0.0119, multigravidae p=0.2717. Maternal malaria: all gravities p=0.0002, paucigravidae p=0.0375, multigravidae p=0.6267. Placental malaria: all gravities p=0.0258, paucigravidae p=0.0124, multigravidae p=0.2472. Low birthweight: all gravities p=0.0821, paucigravidae p=0.1528, multigravidae p=0.4682. Maternal anaemia: all gravities p=0.0425, paucigravidae 0.1012, multigravidae p=0.5735. Maternal moderate anaemia: all gravities p=0.1657, paucigravidae p=0.3732, multigravidae p=0.0008. Preterm delivery: all gravities p=0.0705, paucigravidae p=0.0944, multigravidae 0.9936. Maternal haemoglobin: all gravities p=0.0376, paucigravidae p=0.0177, multigravidae p=0.0704. Birthweight: all gravities p=0.0191, paucigravidae p=0.0154, multigravidae p=0.6040.

** Moderate anaemia: Haemoglobin <9 g/dl or <8 g/dl or <7 g/dl, as defined by each study

Table 2: Relative risk reduction associated with each incremental dose of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for low prevalence outcomes or outcomes with limited availability, 1993-2020

Outcome and resistance category*	Number of studies	Number of participants	Pooled protective effectiveness [†] % Relative Risk Reduction (RRR) (95% CI) or mean difference (95% CI)	P‡	I ² , %	P-trend over resistance categories
Maternal clinical malaria (at least one episode during follow-up)						
All studies	9	8240	25.2 (8.4, 39.0)	0.0051	92.6	
Low resistance	4	1522	16.2 (-5.0, 33.1)	0.12	8.9	
Moderate resistance	4	6301	29.7 (8.0, 46.2)	0.0103	97.0	
High resistance	1	417	-19.3 (-111.9, 32.8)	0.55	-	0.5780
Very-high resistance	0	-	-	-	-	
Any positive histology placenta						
All studies	18	10,498	11.8 (5.7, 17.5)	0.0002	63.6	
Low resistance	5	2219	12.5 (2.0, 21.9)	0.0211	30.8	
Moderate resistance	4	2487	13.7 (-4.0, 28.3)	0.12	78.8	
High resistance	7	4216	16.1 (3.8, 26.9)	0.0122	55.8	0.9530
Very-high resistance	2	1576	3.2 (-5.2, 11.0)	0.44	38.6	
Active placental malaria infection by histology						
All studies	19	10,131	22.8 (14.6, 30.3)	<.0001	62.2	
Low resistance	4	1798	24.7 (11.4, 36.1)	0.0007	0.0	
Moderate resistance	7	3331	29.9 (17.5, 40.5)	<.0001	76.3	
High resistance	7	4301	16.9 (2.2, 29.3)	0.0258	44.8	0.9250
Very-high resistance	1	701	3.3 (-26.6, 26.2)	0.81	0.0	
Pigment in placental histology						
All studies	15	7799	22.0 (10.3, 32.2)	0.0005	82.9	
Low resistance	5	2512	9.3 (-10.5, 25.6)	0.33	50.6	
Moderate resistance	3	1642	20.3 (8.2, 30.7)	0.0016	0.0	
High resistance	6	2770	33.7 (15.4, 48.0)	0.0009	82.5	0.3339
Very-high resistance	1	875	5.5 (-2.2, 12.6)	0.15	.	
Stillbirths						
Studies with a clear definition of stillbirth that excluded abortions	17	38,363	30.3 (-6.5, 54.3)	0.10	88.5	
All studies	44	62,788	30.0 (17.4, 40.7)	<.0001	80.2	
Low resistance	19	21,564	35.0 (16.8, 49.2)	0.0006	82.1	
Moderate resistance	13	30,195	34.6 (2.9, 56.0)	0.0355	87.2	
High resistance	10	6558	2.2 (-25.0, 23.4)	0.86	0.0	0.2494
Very-high resistance	2	4471	-1.1 (-27.2, 19.7)	0.93	0.0	
Maternal postpartum haemorrhage						
All studies	3	3821	31.6 (9.0-48.6)	0.0092	21.0	
Pre-eclampsia and eclampsia						
All studies	2	3080	41.8 (-35.6-75.0)	0.2096	85.9	
Cord blood malaria infection						
All studies	20	16784	19.3 (11.9, 26.2)	<.0001	0.0	
Low resistance	6	4740	25.7 (13.2, 36.4)	0.0002	0.0	
Moderate resistance	7	5435	16.7 (4.9, 27.1)	0.0070	0.0	
High resistance	6	3980	14.3 (-15.2, 36.2)	0.31	0.0	0.2377
Very-high resistance	1	2629	15.2 (-7.1, 32.8)	0.17	-	
Neonatal malaria infection						

All studies	12	6137	27.2 (13.6, 38.7)	0.0003	31.1	
Low resistance	3	1216	28.2 (-30.3, 60.5)	0.28	80.1	
Moderate resistance	8	2292	33.6 (19.0, 45.7)	<.0001	0.0	
High resistance	0	-				0.5809
Very-high resistance	1	2629	15.2 (-7.1, 32.8)	0.17	-	
Foetal anaemia (cord haemoglobin <14 or 12.5 g/dl)						
All studies	9	8734	8.4 (-2.1, 17.8)	0.12	63.1	
Low resistance	2	439	20.7 (-19.9, 47.5)	0.27	80.9	
Moderate resistance	3	1731	10.0 (-4.9, 22.7)	0.18	46.5	
High resistance	3	5879	8.4 (-16.2, 27.8)	0.47	74.8	0.1788
Very-high resistance	1	685	-22.2 (-60.4, 7.0)	0.15	0.0	
Cord haemoglobin (g/dl)						
All studies	6	7134	0.11 (0.02-0.21)	0.0182	0.0	
Newborn head circumference (cm)						
All studies	5	9285	0.11 (0.05-0.16)	0.0001	0.0	
Newborn length (cm)						
All studies	3	1769	0.29 (0.08-0.50)	0.0058	0.0	

* SP resistance definition based on outcome in univariate metaregression for any malaria at the time of delivery (lowest p-value and tau² of evaluation of definitions using stepwise incrementation of *dhps* Ala437Gly, Lys540Glu and Ala581Gly):
 -Low: *Pfdhps*-A437G <75% (Central/West Africa) or *Pfdhps*-K540E <40% (East/southern Africa);
 -Moderate: *Pfdhps*-A437G >=75% (Central/West Africa) or *Pfdhps*-K540E 40-60% & *Pfdhps*-A581G <5% (East/southern Africa);

-High: *Pfdhps*-K540E >=60 & *Pfdhps*-A581G <5% (East/southern Africa);

-Very-high: *Pfdhps*-K540E >=60 & *Pfdhps*-A581G >=5% (East/southern Africa).

† Pooled effect per incremental SP dose obtained by meta-analysis

‡ P-value for Z-test that the risk reduction or the weighted mean difference is 0

Table 3: Adverse events prevalence reported in trials with an IPTp-SP arm, 1993-2020

Outcome	No of comparisons	No of women in IPTp-SP arm	Pooled prevalence in IPTp-SP arm, %, (95% CI) *	P (z) *	I ²	Median prevalence (%), range, IPTp-SP arm	Median prevalence range in comparison arms, %
Abortion	36	20,008	0.69 (0.47, 0.94)	<0.0001	63.5	0.74, 0.0-4.15	0.0-6.88
Congenital abnormalities	22	14,939	0.50 (0.28, 0.77)	<0.0001	65.8	0.56, 0.0-2.51	0.0-4.49
Maternal deaths	25	17,949	0.11 (0.05, 0.18)	<0.0001	0.0	0.18, 0.0-1.04	0.0-0.71
Neonatal death [†]	25	12,880	1.91 (1.41, 2.47)	<0.0001	75.9	1.84, 0.0-4.35	0.0-5.87
Perinatal death	12	10,272	3.28 (2.22, 4.53)	<0.0001	90.4	3.45, 1.03-6.23	1.08-8.02
Serious adverse events	8	6571	3.84 (2.20, 5.88)	<0.0001	92.5	3.90, 0.62-8.97‡	0.0-9.74
Maternal adverse events	16	8122	14.28 (4.88,27.46)	<0.0001	99.5	5.50, 0.63-62.1	0.48-89.94
Maternal skin reaction	11	4186	0.40 (0.17, 0.70)	<0.0001	24.1	0.21, 0.0-1.10‡	0.0-1.21
Maternal itching	8	2862	2.87 (1.00, 5.57)	<0.0001	91.9	4.33, 0.0-7.41	0.0-8.13
Maternal headache	10	5413	7.37 (3.90, 11.80)	<0.0001	96.6	7.38, 0.67-18.52‡	0.67-21.10
Maternal nausea	14	7379	4.62 (2.47, 7.37)	<0.0001	95.8	3.80, 0.0-15.57‡	0.0-35.91
Maternal vomiting	14	7384	5.43 (3.00, 8.51)	<0.0001	96.2	6.41, 0.0-15.41‡	0.0-53.99
Maternal dizziness	12	6681	7.69 (4.82, 11.16)	<0.0001	95.6	7.38, 0.67-20.28	2.33-56.04
Abdominal pain	6	3816	2.46 (0.78, 4.95)	0.0001	93.3	2.25, 0.0-7.23‡	0.67-11.03
Neonatal jaundice	11	5349	3.21 (0.98, 6.58)	0.0001	97.0	2.67, 0.0-15.97	0.12-20.41

CM, case management.

*Metaprop-procedure Stata 17. P(z) for prevalence: p-value for Z-test that the weighted mean is 0. P(z) for Risk ratio: p-value for Z-test that the Risk ratio is 1.

[†]Neonatal death: newborn death in period of birth to 28 days, for Briand 2009 and Mbaye 2006 up to 6 weeks postpartum

[‡]Maternal SAE: Three additional studies reported outcome as incidence per person-year (Desai 2015, Kakuru 2016, Kajubi 2019) range 0.07-0.41/person-year; range alternative arms: 0.10-0.41/person-year. Maternal rash: one study reported outcome as incidence per person year (Desai 2015): 0.03/person-year, alternative arms 0.0/person-year. Maternal headache: Three additional studies reported outcome as incidence per person-year (Desai 2015, Kakuru 2016, Kajubi 2019): range 0.24-3.21/person-year. Range alternative arms: 0.19-3.19/person-year. Maternal nausea: Two additional studies reported outcome as incidence per person-year (Desai 2015, Kakuru 2016): range 0.04-0.9/person-year. Range alternative arms: 0.0-0.12/person-year. Maternal vomiting: Three additional studies reported outcome as incidence per person-year (Desai 2015, Kakuru 2016, Kajubi 2019): range 0.9-0.24/person-year. Range alternative arms: 0.0-0.24/person-year (5 arms). Maternal abdominal pain: Three additional studies reported outcome as incidence per person-year (Desai 2015, Kakuru 2016, Kajubi 2019): range 0.51-4.5/person-year. Range alternative arms: 0.2-4.2/person-year (5 arms).

Table 4: Adverse events reported in trials with an IPTp-SP arm compared to a placebo or case management arm, 1993-2020

	IPTp-SP studies with placebo or CM (comparisons)	Events/total in IPTp-SP arm	Events/total in comparison arm	Pooled Risk ratio IPTp-SP arm vs. placebo/CM (95% CI)	I ²	P (z) *
Abortion	7 (9)	72/5414	84/5009	0.82 (0.60-1.13)	0.0	0.23
Congenital abnormalities	2 (2)	6/2281	3/2296	1.71 (0.41-7.12)	0.0	0.46
Maternal deaths	5 (6)	15/4378	11/4377	1.17 (0.49-2.80)	0.0	0.72
Neonatal death†	5 (6)	103/4518	100/4205	0.93 (0.61-1.42)	41.5	0.73
Perinatal death	3 (3)	125/2887	123/2900	0.98 (0.69-1.40)	44.4	0.93
Maternal adverse events	2 (3)	25/1981	27/1360	0.56 (0.30-1.01)	13.97	0.056
Maternal skin reaction	2 (2)	5/733	6/739	1.24 (0.34-4.58)	0.0	0.75
Neonatal jaundice	2 (3)	97/1258	61/925	0.84 (0.63-1.13)	0.0	0.26

†Neonatal death: newborn death in period of birth to 28 days, for Mbaye 2006 up to 6 weeks postpartum